

Sample Name: PP UV 5-10 μm

Material: Polypropylene

Size: 5-10 μm

Production Partner: TNO

Storage Conditions: Refrigerated and dark

Summary

Physical Characteristics

- Median diameter (D_{50_v}) = 8,25 μm
- Particles have an irregular morphology
- $4,3 \times 10^{11}$ particles per gram
- 13545 cm^2/g surface area

Chemical Characteristics

- >99% C_3H_6 (PP) determined by XRF
- C=O peak (1715 cm^{-1}) due to oxidation observed in FTIR spectrum
- Cathodoluminescence shows typical PP spectrum with increased intensity due to oxidation ($\sim 415 \text{ nm}$)

Description of terms

- $D[4,3]$: Volume mean (μm)
- $D[3,2]$: Surface area mean (μm)
- $D[2,1]$: Spherical particle mean (μm)
- $D[1,0]$: Number length mean (μm)
- D_{50_v} : Median diameter (volume basis, μm)
- D_{50_N} : Median diameter (number basis, μm)
- N_w : Number of particles per gram plastic ($\#/g$)
- A_w : Surface area of particles per gram plastic (cm^2/g)

Particle Size Distribution (using Static Light Scattering (SLS) provided by TNO)

D[4,3]	D[3,2]	D[2,1]	D[1,0]	D50 _N	D50 _V	N _w	A _w
10,68	4,92	1,49	0,67	0,48	8,25	4.3×10^{11}	13545

Chemical Composition (using XRF provided by Malvern Panalytical)

Chemical formula	Concentration (%)
C_3H_6	99,937
Element	Concentration (ppm)
Si	227
P	73
S	10
Cl	449
K	54
Ca	88
Ti	3
Cr	83
Mn	4
Fe	223
Ni	15
Cu	1
Zn	1
Mo	1
Pb	1

Chemical Bonding (Using μ -FTIR provided by TNO)

Cathodoluminescence Spectroscopy (provided by TNO)

